

THEORETICAL FEATURES OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS' DEVELOPMENT OF VIOLIN PERFORMANCE SKILLS

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Abstract: In this thesis, comments are made about the scientific-theoretical features of future music teachers' development of violin performance skills.

Key words: Higher education, music culture, musical ability, scientific analysis, scientific approach, violin performance skills.

Introduction.

The process of training highly qualified specialists in the field of musical performance art is multifaceted in its composition, has its own characteristics at the level of higher education and at the level of the nature of the performer.

Reforming the system of training musical instruments in higher education involves solving a number of contradictions and a set of unresolved tasks. In the recent past, many leading experts, both teachers and psychologists (*E. B. Abdullin, Yu. P. Azarov, Sh. A. Amonashvili, O. A. Blokh, A. A. Bodalev, Z. A. Malkova, L. I. Novikova, E. D. Dneprov, A. B. Petrovsky, G. M. Tsypin*) and others. The intolerance of the standardization of the educational process, the superiority of the authoritarian style of teaching, the formality of the pedagogical activity, the real difference between education and training, the violation of the continuity in the structure of the organization of the educational process and its measurement were noted. In the field of violin and creative activity, the shortcomings in question seem particularly inexorable. The current system of professional music education carries the burden of the common shortcomings, paradoxes and diseases of our society. Based on them, the following were established:

- to strictly combine the content and forms of training of specialists;
- separation of musical education from the needs and tasks of general cultural and aesthetic development of the population;
- the goal is primarily to achieve the laureate foundation by individual students;
- a one-sided focus on technology to the detriment of broad artistic education, and finally, neglecting many, including social problems of

musical art, which do not fit into the single stereotypical coordinates of the content of music education¹.

The new stage of the development of the professional system of music education revealed a number of contradictions that are on the agenda of the reform of higher education today. "The reform of the local musical upbringing and education system identified and strengthened the conflicts between educational goals and methods of achieving them, tasks set on the agenda, and outdated music-pedagogical "technologies", "Music-pedagogical" technologies, and educational methods.

The above contradictions occur in several directions:

- conceptual approaches to educating and teaching students.
- Content of the educational process of violin performance art.
- Forms and methods of daily pedagogical work in the violin class.

On the other hand, something must be said about the tradition of the violin performance school, which has gained a high reputation in the field of world music culture. In this phrase, the school appears as a set of certain aesthetic and professional norms, rules, and instructions. The school is a unity of unique views (*musical, performing and pedagogical principles, methodological approaches*) of its founders and supporters. The school is similar to a certain level of aesthetic, spiritual consciousness of the performing artist.

An urgent issue in our research is the study of the modern musical functional-harmonic system, which is constantly developing. This aspect K. A. Ushakov's it is reflected in research. One of the main features of violin performance is direct contact with the audience, opens of the musician. The violinist always addresses the hall, the audience. As an academic performer, he does not distance himself from the public, he is closely connected with the audience, making direct contact with him, making him an active partner. A musician should be a meaningful and charming conversationalist.

The sense of rhythm is the perception and repetition of temporal relationships in music. Metrical senses are associated with a constant alternation of supported and unsupported sounds. Such an exchange of strong and weak jissas is a reflection of the universal processes of life, which are associated with the periodic exchange of periods of activity and rest. In life, after tension, there is always a rest, the increase in activity leads to its decrease. The famous French teacher of rhythm J. Jacques-Dalcroze said that space and time

¹ Якупов, А.Н. Музыкальная коммуникация. Вопросы теории и практики управления А.Н. Якупов. - Москва - Новосибирск, 2003. - С. 133.

are filled with matter that obeys the laws of eternal rhythm. The tempo-rhythmic structure of the work is the organizational basis of music, it reflects the main characteristic of music, its temporary nature.

According to the Russian researcher G. Kogan, musicians performing academic traditions can not only interpret a separate episode or a work as a whole, but also improvise its text, the music itself. But here there is already a transition from the field of performing arts to compositional creativity. "*However, you can regret the times when creativity and performance formed a single, unified art, and performers could talk to the audience not only through the words of other people*"², writes G. Kogan.

It should be noted that listening to violin performance standards with improvisations of famous violinists develops associative-combinatorial, analytical thinking, aesthetic taste, special abilities - the ability to "empathize" through musical hearing, memory, awareness and understanding, that is, any composition- understanding the artistic idea of improvisation. Violin performance represents the factor of creative education through the development of creativity.

In playing an instrument, the personality of the performer becomes an organic part of it, the musical idea is perceived by the listener as an emotional and spiritual experience of the personal essence of the musician, which is manifested in the process of creating music by itself, and the artistic quality of such music may be related to the spiritual, intellectual image of its creator.

It is known that most of the musical works were originally focused on wind and percussion instruments. The specific features of performance on these instruments had a great impact on the formation and development of performance in general. The peculiarity of modern violin performance requires improvisational skills and the ability to creatively, reliably and non-standard processing of various thematic materials from the player-musician, arranger, composer, as well as ensemble or orchestra leader. In musical improvisation, there is no separation of the composer (*musical composition*) and performer (*interpretation*) functions, they form an organic unit and are simultaneously performed by the improvising musician.

Renowned violinists (*Staff Smith, Joe Venuti, Stefano Grapelli, Jean-Luc Ponti, Paul Miyagi, Dide Lockwood, David Goloshchekin*) offer their performance experience and skill as a result of following their pedagogical systems. Often, these works are based on any modern direction of performance development or

² Коган, Г.М. Избранные статьи / Г.М. Коган. - М.: Советский композитор, 1972.

the style of a particular musician, and are not a coherent educational system at all. As a result, a new violinist who relies on the above method risks losing his identity.

Not every violinist is capable of becoming a true virtuoso performer. The challenge comes from the difference in the skills required in academic performance. The pedagogical system of learning to play the violin "classically" often does not give the necessary creative freedom to the musician. The negative aspects of this system are manifested when the musician wants to perform freely and finds slavery in the performance. The concept of "*freedom of performance*" refers to the possibility of direct expressive manipulation during the performance of the work.

Today, approaches to effective activity and creative development mainly reflect the paradigm of developing students' performance culture.

The analysis of the violin and pedagogical literature allows to identify a number of principles, the use of which allows for the effective implementation of the process of developing the performance culture of students.

Directional principle. The artistic and pedagogical process in the violin class should be aimed at developing the performing apparatus (performance technique), as well as solving educational problems, expanding opportunities, and increasing the intellectual level of students. The musician is in many ways a thinker who must appear before us both as a master and as a creator. Confirming this opinion, O. F. Shulpyakov notes: "*a characteristic feature of performance is that between the presented (ideal musical images) and real (real) images, there is always a field of motor skill, which not only capable of raising to the first level, but inevitably brings the former closer to the possibilities of the latter. In other words: not only hearing and aesthetic consciousness affect action, but actions themselves - according to the principle of thought - reflection - on the development and improvement of consciousness and hearing affects.*"³

According to G. M. Sipin⁴, The formula "see - hear - perform" is of great importance in musical performance. Often in practice, according to the researcher, due to the violation of the "internal hearing-performance" scheme, its components are replaced, which leads students to "do their work with their hands" and hearing passively receives sounds.

³ Шульпяков, О.Ф. Музыкально-исполнительская техника и художественный образ. - М.: Музыка, 1986. - С. 39.

⁴ Цыпин, Г.М. Психология музыкальной деятельности; проблемы, суждения, мнения / Г.М. Цыпин. - М.: Интерпракс, 1994. - 384 с.

If in the process of developing the performance culture of violin students, you learn to learn not every single situation, but to learn the ornaments, "*to learn the little but important things so that everything will come out later*", then you can achieve not only effective, but also high-quality musicians. . In the theory of performance, O. F. Shulpyakov identified three levels of generalization: "*understanding the laws of the musical language, generalizing and systematizing the technical-semantic organization of the performance, and finally synthesizing the playing technique along the lines of motor sensations.*"⁵. These levels cover the entire process of training a violinist student, from its highest artistic and semantic manifestations to the rational organization of the motor apparatus designed to realize performance intentions.

The theoretical foundation of the levels of generalization reveals certain perspectives for practical pedagogy. First of all, it can be manifested in the activation of artistic thinking, which allows the musician to develop more quickly, to engage in creative, analytical and creative activities. The development of a methodology based on the generalization of technical and textural techniques equips students with a flexible tool technique, which allows you to quickly learn works, read notes from a sheet and master creative freedom. The transmission of motor sensations characteristic of the third level forms the motor-rational performance technique that allows achieving artistic goals in the most economical way.

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